

Integrated Infrastructure for Open Science¹

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To realise the vision of Open Science and achieve its goals, Open Science practices must be integrated into the scientific workflow. With appropriate infrastructure, including hardware, software, and personal support, research institutes enable their researchers to effortlessly comply with legal and regulatory requirements (such as the GDPR), institutional policies (on data management, ethics, and security), Open Science principles (such as FAIR data and software), and Research Integrity codes of conduct (promoting transparency and traceability).

Of course, institutions must have policies in place for these matters, and researchers should be well-informed about them. However, compliance should not rely solely on researchers' knowledge, willingness, and ability to follow policies and regulations. Instead, well-designed infrastructure should ensure compliance by making it the natural and unavoidable choice. If the infrastructure is simple, appealing, and seamlessly integrated into research workflows, researchers will adopt it effortlessly. And if the infrastructure itself is compliant with policies and regulations, researchers' compliance will follow as a matter of course.

Relevant infrastructures include those supporting open scholarly communication (OSC), research data management (RDM), and open research information (ORI). Each of these infrastructures is made up of multiple components, many of which are shared across them. Ultimately, they form a single, comprehensive, and integrated infrastructure, as will become clear in the discussion below.

1. Open Scholarly Communication (OSC)

The core of Open Science is that researchers share their work as early and as extensively as possible. This goes far beyond publishing scholarly articles on their (most appealing) results; it also includes research data and everything leading up to it, such as research plans, protocols (for data collection, interventions, and instrumentation), tests and questionnaires, lab journals, data analysis plans, software, and source code. Sharing these materials allows other researchers to engage with the research at an early stage, provide feedback, and build upon existing work. Making them available also enhances scientific integrity by ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the research process. And it enables society to access and learn from scientific insights, fostering broader engagement with research and its outcomes.

A straightforward way for universities to share all types of research materials is by using their institutional repositories (see Figure 1). A repository allows for the publication of all kinds of university outputs—not only scholarly texts and research materials but also other academic contributions, such as educational resources and anything else universities wish to share with the world (see the blue column in Figure 1). The use of their own repositories has the added advantage that, in terms of digital sovereignty, universities retain full control over the academic output produced and published under their management and responsibility.

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² Earlier versions date from October 2024 and March 2025. These informed the [Strategic Plan Integrated Infrastructure for Open Science](#). Compared to the March 2025 version, the current version includes a table with desired characteristics of the integrated infrastructure, as discussed at the May 2025 meeting of the rectors of the Dutch universities. This version also incorporates comments by Arjan Schalken, which are gratefully acknowledged.

To make publication via repositories more attractive for researchers, institutional repositories should be part of a federated network of repositories, accessible through a publication platform or portal with proper indexing, dissemination, and other enhancements (see the green column in Figure 1). Other types of repositories could also be integrated into this network (see the yellow column in Figure 1). Such a network can also support additional services, such as tools that help researchers choose an appropriate publication venue or platform.³

Figure 1: Open scholarly communication through repositories.

The process should be as seamless as possible for researchers, with publication being largely automated. Any peer review could take place post-publication, voluntarily conducted by interested readers. The publication platform could also incorporate the PRC (Publish-Review-Curate) model and support various metrics, including both traditional and next-generation indicators. Additionally, a Research Data Exchange (RDX), as found in the RDM infrastructure, could be linked to the publication platform to regulate access to certain publications and, if necessary, impose conditions for their use.

As a result, an OSC infrastructure would consist of components such as:

1. Institutional repositories, and possibly a national repository for universities without their own dedicated repositories.
2. Institutional information systems (CRISs), possibly supplemented by a national CRIS.
3. Institutional quality oversight, to ensure that only verified and appropriate content is published. This may include internal (peer) review processes to assess the validity and quality of the content before publication.
4. Institutional administrative oversight, to verify the correctness and completeness of metadata, and ensure that items for publication are accompanied by relevant licenses or copyright notices.

³ An example is the [WUR Journal Browser](#).

5. An institutional portal for researchers to upload and submit items to the institutional repository. The portal should also facilitate the workflow between researchers and support staff for academic and administrative oversight.
6. A network connecting all institutional repositories and organising metadata, ensuring that it is accurate, complete, non-redundant, and properly catalogued (for example through harvesting and aggregation, using services such as OpenAIRE or OpenAlex). Other repositories, whether national or international, disciplinary or general, may also choose to participate.
7. A national publication platform or portal for the central dissemination of all items in the repositories, presented in an engaging and user-friendly way. This platform could be integrated with the national repository mentioned under number 1.
8. The publication platform should have proper indexing of all items, ensuring discoverability through well-known academic discovery and indexing services, which are currently predominantly provided by commercial parties (such as Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science).
9. The publication platform should include a review facility, allowing readers to provide reviews of published items. Reviews should be visible on the platform and linked to the original work, encouraging authors to publish improved versions. The review process could follow the PRC (Publish-Review-Curate) model, supporting continuous improvement and curation of all scholarly outputs.
10. The platform might also include a discussion facility, such as a blog, forum, or commenting system, enabling researchers and the wider community to engage in discussions about published items. Comments and discussion contributions should be connected to the relevant items and visible to all users.
11. The publication platform should provide both traditional and next-generation metrics for *all* published items, tracking views, downloads, citations, and engagement, including reviews and discussion contributions. (Reviews are considered published items too and should be tracked in the same way, ensuring recognition not only for original work but also for evaluative contributions.)
12. The publication platform should include a faceted search feature for easy navigation.
13. The publication platform should offer a system to regulate access to its items, depending on the user consulting the platform.
14. The publication platform may include an AI tool that provides popularised summaries of scholarly literature.

This tentative list highlights that infrastructure encompasses not only hardware and software but also personal support. Institutional quality control (as in components 3 and 4) is essential and must be organised within the institution. It is up to the institution to determine the level of rigour in this oversight, which may also depend on the type of item being deposited in the repository (e.g., text, data, etc.).

Yet, since the process from the repository (yellow column) to further dissemination (green column) is fully automated, the review before depositing an item in the repository is the institution's only opportunity to intervene. Another important factor is that, in this publishing

model,⁴ the author's affiliation with the institution serves as a key indicator of the quality of the work (and vice versa!).

The institution may also want to regulate access (component 13), for example, by imposing an embargo or retention period on an item, setting access conditions based on specific terms of use, or ensuring that the published item includes the appropriate copyright notice or license.

2. Research Data Management (RDM)

Open Science principles call for research data to be FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. However, data sharing is subject to conditions imposed by laws and regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), as well as data sovereignty concerns, which must be considered to protect the interests of the university and its researchers. RDM policies may therefore distinguish between FAIR archiving, which is closed, and FAIR publishing, which is open. All data should be archived with full provenance in a closed repository (FAIR for the institute), while a selection of data suitable for publication should be made openly available (FAIR for the outside world).⁵

Implementing RDM policies requires three types of storage, as illustrated in Figure 2. A comprehensive RDM infrastructure would potentially consist of (at least) the following components:

1. Temporary workspace for data for data storage, processing, and analysis during the active phase of a research project. The workspace can also support shared environments for collaboration, including with external partners.
2. Closed storage for archiving data packages containing raw or sensitive data and full provenance descriptions, ensuring long-term preservation and compliance with security and privacy regulations.
3. Publication platform for publishing data packages, openly but subject to use conditions, regulated by a research data exchange.
4. A 'research data exchange' (RDX)⁶ or 'data access broker' (DAB)⁷ for conditional data sharing in a responsible manner, subject to agreement to terms of use.
5. An archive system to track and log who accesses research data through the RDX, archive agreements to terms of use, monitor usage, and enable auditing of data access.
6. A temporary secure workspace for analysis of (sensitive) data enabled by a 'trusted research environment' (TRE),⁸ such as SANE.⁹
7. A research data hub (RDH)¹⁰ for transferring data to either a closed archive or an open publication platform, including essential metadata.

⁴ The model fits with [earlier ideas](#) about scholarly communication ([Diamond Open Access Publication Platforms](#), the [University Journals](#) platform) and the need for public infrastructure to ensure digital sovereignty ([Public Infrastructure](#)).

⁵ For an example of general RDM policy principles see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10954656>

⁶ For a short explanation of the RDX see <https://zenodo.org/records/8269273> or the [AMDEX website](#)

⁷ For a short explanation of the DAB see <https://dab.surf.nl/about/>

⁸ For an explanation of TRE see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4594703>

⁹ For a short explanation of SANE see <https://www.surf.nl/en/themes/research-infrastructure/sane-secure-environment-for-analysing-sensitive-data>

¹⁰ For a short description of the RDH see <https://zenodo.org/records/11201003>

Figure 2: Workspace storage, archiving, and publication of data.

Note: Temporary storage will be provided as WORKSPACE storage for data processing and analysis, for the duration of the research project. Immediately after data collection, and at any other appropriate time, the researcher will submit data packages for archiving. The ARCHIVE stores data packages with full provenance for an indefinite period, closed, accessible only after approval by the Dean. Data packages suitable for publication are submitted to the PUBLICATION PLATFORM, which holds data packages for an indefinite period, open, but subject to use conditions, regulated by the Research Data Exchange (RDX).

8. Supporting data management software, such as Yoda/iRODS,¹¹ to manage and transfer data and metadata between storage systems.
9. A research registration portal for ethics reviews, data management plans, project control, archiving and publication of data, etc., with automated support and workflows to reduce the administrative burden on both researchers and support staff.
10. User-friendly interface enabling researchers and support staff to easily access and navigate all components of the RDM infrastructure, including a referral system to guide users to relevant resources, experts, or services, and facilitating the workflow and collaboration.
11. Academic oversight to verify that data packages comply with FAIR principles, contain complete provenance descriptions, including documentation of data collection methods. For datasets intended for publication, checks should ensure that no sensitive information is disclosed.
12. Administrative oversight to verify the correctness and completeness of metadata, ensure compliance with contractual obligations, terms of use, and informed consent requirements. For datasets intended for publication, checks should ensure that data packages include terms of use and access conditions, as well as appropriate licenses, if applicable.

As in the OSC infrastructure, quality control is crucial in the RDM infrastructure (components 8 and 12), for the same reasons mentioned earlier. With research data, there is an additional concern as the institution must prevent researchers from accidentally uploading AVG-sensitive

¹¹ For a short explanation of Yoda/ iRODS see <https://www.surf.nl/en/services/yoda-hosting>

information¹² for publication or from inadvertently failing to meet contractual obligations. Ideally, data packages would also be checked against the FAIR principles, ensuring that an independent third party could navigate the data and replicate the analysis results. It is up to the institutions to decide the extent to which they wish to implement such controls.

Another important aspect of the RDM infrastructure is access regulation through a research data exchange (component 4). While legal scholars generally agree that ownership of research data does not exist and that copyright rights and typical licenses do not apply, access to the data can still be regulated, subject to terms of use. As an option, institutions may restrict access to data by allowing statistical analyses within a trusted environment but not permitting the download of the data.

Workflows in RDM can become complex, as the gatekeepers for quality control (both academic and administrative) will likely need to consult various entities within the institution. This will function effectively only if user-friendly interfaces are in place to facilitate the referral system (components 9 and 8).¹³

3. Open Research Information (ORI)

Research information includes all metadata about research activities, such as information on researchers (profiles, affiliations, contributions), publications (articles, books, reports, etc.; cf. OSC), research projects (grant proposals, funding details, collaborations, ongoing and completed research), research data (metadata, access conditions, identifiers; cf. RDM), funding organizations (sources, programmes, calls, success rates), and research evaluation metrics (traditional metrics such as citation counts, next-generation metrics,¹⁴ other research impact indicators), etc. By making such information openly available, ORI enhances transparency, collaboration, and responsible research assessment.

ORI infrastructure should improve interoperability between systems, ensure efficient resource use, and safeguard academic digital sovereignty.¹⁵ Maintaining control over research information is essential to prevent reliance on proprietary systems that may restrict access, impose high costs, or limit reusability. Furthermore, reliance on commercial parties may bias the results if not all data sources are covered or if some are weighted disproportionately. To ensure that research information remains open, accessible, and under the governance of the academic community, an open knowledge base is needed; see Figure 3. Such a knowledge base can also support the ongoing enrichment and reuse of research information.

This OKB can be populated with all the metadata associated with the items listed in the OSC and RDM infrastructures. In addition, universities have other information to share, such as management information (e.g., annual reports, including from other domains than the research domain). Other organisations, such as research funding organisations and service providers, also hold relevant research information. Universities can feed the OKB through their institutional CRIS, but additional functionality may be required; an enhanced and more comprehensive CRIS may therefore be necessary. Furthermore, the OKB may incorporate metadata from external bibliometric databases, including open sources and, if legally and technically possible, also

¹² The AVG (Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming) is the Dutch implementation of the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation)

¹³ The University of Amsterdam is extending its existing web application that integrates research registration and user interfaces into a one-stop shop that links to various other infrastructure components. See <https://zenodo.org/records/15031512>

¹⁴ [Next Generation Metrics for Scientific and Scholarly Research in Europe](#)

¹⁵ Seven Guiding Principles for Open Research Information: <https://zenodo.org/records/6074944>

from commercial sources, which may require additional agreements on terms of use, licenses, and data access conditions.¹⁶

Figure 3: Open research information.

Note: For reasons of readability, the figure presents the main information flows in a simplified form (from left to right). In practice, information flows are iterative and bidirectional, metadata may be enriched and fed back into institutional systems, and external sources can continuously contribute information. In addition to aggregation and dissemination, such an infrastructure also enables reuse of research information for purposes such as monitoring, analysis, and the development of additional services, for example publication-based metrics and indicators, as well as open access and open science monitors.

If the OKB is equipped with a conditional access system, similar to the RDX for research data, access can be regulated based on the information users require and their access rights, for example in cases where information is subject to confidentiality constraints at the institutional or personal level, or other applicable access conditions. Dedicated APIs should enable external parties to develop new tools and services using the information in the OKB. An ORI infrastructure like this allows universities to maintain control over the information they make available while creating a level playing field for all external parties that wish to use it. Such infrastructure would contain components such as the following.

1. Institutional CRISs (Current Research Information Systems), and possibly a national CRIS for institutions without their own dedicated systems, to transfer relevant information to the Open Knowledge Base (OKB).
2. An interface for uploading, reviewing, managing information and metadata, including, where applicable, accompanying terms of use. Such an interface could be used by institutions that provide information, but also by other stakeholders to provide feedback and improve information.

¹⁶ For example, open sources such as OpenAIRE and OpenAlex, and commercial sources such as Scopus and Web of Science.

3. Institutional administrative oversight, to verify the correctness and completeness of metadata and management information before it is contributed to the OKB.
4. Centralised storage (the OKB itself) for all research information (metadata), aggregating information from institutional CRISs and other data sources to ensure consistency, accuracy, and interoperability.
5. An integration system that harvests metadata from the various CRISs and, where legally possible, from external bibliometric databases.¹⁷
6. A validation mechanism to manage metadata from different sources (institutional CRISs, funders, bibliometric databases, etc.) preventing duplication and ensuring consistency by resolving discrepancies, such as when different versions of the same item have different PIDs in different sources.
7. Conditional access mechanisms, to control access to sensitive or restricted research information based on predefined terms of use, dependent on the user's role, affiliation, or specific access rights.
8. A faceted search system, possibly through integration with the OSC publication platform.
9. Research evaluation metrics, including traditional citation metrics, next-generation metrics, research impact indicators, for assessing the quality and reach of research outputs, possibly through integration with the OSC publication platform.
10. APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) for data sharing and automation, enabling automated data exchange that allows external third parties (public and private) to develop tools and services based on the ORI.
11. An archive system to track and log who accesses research information through the access mechanisms or APIs (components 7 and 10), archive agreements to terms of use, monitor usage, and enable auditing.

These components form a flexible and secure ORI infrastructure that supports research management, collaboration and access, while protecting sensitive information. Maintaining control over research information is critical as universities rely on it for their decision-making and evaluation. Digital sovereignty must be maintained to ensure that institutions can manage their own research data, metadata and management information without relying on proprietary systems that limit their options. An OKB helps to prevent data lock-in and vendor lock-in, to limit private influence over research infrastructure, and to ensure access to metadata.

4. Integrating OSC, RDM, and ORI in a unified approach

While the OSC, RDM, and ORI infrastructures, as tentatively outlined in the previous sections, each serve distinct functions, they share various components. Table 1 gives an overview of components that may be shared between them. The purpose of this comparison is to highlight the necessity of integrating these three infrastructures into a single, coherent infrastructure. Instead of developing separate, isolated systems for OSC, RDM, and ORI, a unified approach ensures greater efficiency, interoperability, and sustainability. Many of the core components, such as repositories, access control mechanisms, and user interfaces, are already functionally similar across these infrastructures. By integrating them into a shared infrastructure, duplication of effort can be avoided, so that we can benefit from a more streamlined and cost-effective system for managing research outputs, research data, metadata, and management information.

¹⁷ The Jisc Publication Router may be a useful model: <https://pubrouter.jisc.ac.uk/about/>

Of course, each infrastructure also has specific components that require dedicated solutions: OSC focuses on publishing, peer review, and broad dissemination; RDM prioritises data security, provenance, and controlled sharing; and ORI is centred on metadata aggregation, research assessment, and interoperability. These domain-specific requirements underscore the need for an integrated yet flexible infrastructure, where shared components are harmonised while distinct functionalities remain available to meet the unique needs of OSC, RDM, and ORI.

Table 1: Common infrastructure components.

	Open Scholarly Communication (OSC)	Research Data Management (RDM)	Open Research Information (ORI)
Repositories and centralised storage	Institutional repositories, possibly a national repository.	Repositories are used in RDM, but additional functions are required.	A national repository could serve as storage for metadata of both OSC and RDM.
Institutional information systems (CRISs)	Institutional CRISs, possibly a national CRIS.	The FDH and supporting software serve a similar function.	Institutional CRISs, possibly a national CRIS.
Indexing and dissemination platforms	National publication platform for repository dissemination.	Data publication platform, subject to access conditions.	Integration with OSC publication platform promotes dissemination.
Conditional access mechanisms	Conditional access may apply to specific items in repositories.	Research Data Exchange (RDX) functionality regulates access, subject to terms of use.	Conditional access mechanisms based on user roles or predefined terms.
Metrics and indexing for discoverability and recognition	Traditional and next-gen. metrics, enabling recognition of publishing all types of items.	Traditional and next-generation metrics, enabling recognition of publishing data sets.	Next-generation metrics for research evaluation, using consistent item and researcher PIDs across OSC and RDM.
Faceted search systems	Faceted search for all items in repositories.	Faceted search for data sets.	Faceted search for metadata and management information.
Institutional oversight and quality control	Academic oversight (e.g. review) and administrative checks (e.g. metadata verification, license checks).	Academic oversight (e.g. FAIR compliance) and administrative checks (e.g. metadata, terms of use).	Administrative oversight of metadata and management information.
User interfaces for researchers and support staff	Institutional portal for submitting items to repositories, and organizing the workflow for support staff.	Institutional portal for submitting data sets for archiving or publication, and organizing the workflow for support staff.	Interface for uploading, reviewing, and managing metadata.
Archiving and logging of access	The RDM system of tracking access might serve repository items too.	Archive system to track access to research data, agreements, and audits.	Archive system to track access to research information, agreements, and audits.

5. Requirements of the Integrated Infrastructure

The integrated infrastructure must satisfy various requirements to ensure functionality, sustainability, and alignment with public and institutional values. These requirements are summarised in Table 2.

In developing an integrated infrastructure, careful attention must be given to ensuring that it is federated, modular, and compatible with existing infrastructures. It must be federated, ensuring

that institutions retain control over their local infrastructures and the content of their repositories. It must be modular, allowing institutions to select and integrate only the components they need while ensuring seamless interoperability. In addition, wherever possible, existing infrastructure components should be leveraged rather than replaced, ensuring continuity without unnecessary duplication. Most importantly, while this integrated, federated, and modular infrastructure is being developed at the national level, it must align seamlessly with local institutional infrastructures, other existing infrastructures at both national and international levels, including large discipline-specific infrastructures, and the EOSC infrastructure, which is currently under development (<https://eosc.eu/>).

In addition to these architectural principles, the integrated infrastructure must take into account institutional responsibilities, public values, and the need to maintain trust in academic infrastructure, which are considered preconditions for its development. To safeguard digital sovereignty, the infrastructure should, wherever possible, be built as public infrastructure, ensuring that research institutions retain control over their outputs, data, metadata, and management information. Collaboration with commercial parties remains possible and sometimes necessary, but procurement processes must include clear agreements on ownership, governance, interoperability, and exit strategies to prevent vendor lock-in. Prioritising public values ensures that Open Science remains truly open, independent, and sustainable in the long term.

Table 2: Desired characteristics of the integrated infrastructure

Characteristic	Description
Compliant	The infrastructure should enable researchers to comply with legal and regulatory requirements (e.g. GDPR), institutional policies (e.g. RDM, ethics, security), Open Science principles (e.g. FAIR data, open access), and research integrity codes of conduct (e.g. transparency, traceability).
User-friendly	The infrastructure must be simple and intuitive to use, so that researchers do not turn to non-institutional or non-university solutions. Since the institutional infrastructure is compliant, users will be too, even if they do not have full knowledge of all requirements.
Cost-effective	The infrastructure should support inter-institutional collaboration to reduce duplication and costs, especially since no single institution can independently develop and maintain complete infrastructure.
Integrated	Infrastructures supporting the research practice, including those for OSC, RDM, and ORI, share many common components and should therefore be developed in a coordinated way into a single, integrated, and comprehensive infrastructure.
Modular	The integrated infrastructure should be built in a modular way, so that institutions can adopt modules independently, integrate them with existing local systems, and avoid the need to replace all their entire local infrastructure.
Federated	In a federated infrastructure, components provided by universities and other parties can be integrated without loss of ownership, governance, or control. Responsibility for managing their own infrastructural components can remain with the respective parties.
Interoperable	The infrastructure should make use of existing infrastructures as much as possible, enhancing coherence and reuse, by integrating with or connecting to other infrastructures at the local and (inter)national level, whether disciplinary (e.g. GWIs, ERICs) or generic (e.g. ORE, EOSC).
Digitally sovereign	The infrastructure should guarantee digital sovereignty, ensuring that universities can fulfil their public mission and maintain the security and accessibility of research data, publications, and other outputs. Collaboration with commercial parties remains possible, but only under procurement agreements that specify ownership, governance, interoperability, and exit strategies to prevent vendor lock-in.
Sustainable	In developing the infrastructure, clear agreements on long-term funding, management, and maintenance must be made, so that the infrastructure remains scalable and future-proof, also under changing needs or emerging technologies.